

How to implement Open Science in your group

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#openscience #openMPMI #2023ISMPMI

**The Concept Open Science
might mean different things
to different people**

What does it mean to you?

menti.com
3208 0025

Think of the audience

1. **Your Lab**
2. Co-authors on projects and publications
3. All researchers **globally**
4. Funders, Policy makers, Citizen Scientists, and General Public

Open Science - Democratization of science

- Producing scientific ideas, methods, results, reagents in format as widely accessible by international audience as possible.
- Giving information to everyone on equal footing at the same time.
- Pay attention to documenting research (metadata), reproducibility and interoperability.

Scientific publishing: how have changes over the last 50 years affected scientists?

A recent Royal Society oral history event provided an opportunity to learn from four senior scientists who lived through the changes

Take actions to convince people
Open Science is best for everyone

Utilize tools available today

<https://www.theguardian.com/science/the-word/2015/may/29/publishing-change-50-years-scientists-history>

**Convince the PI,
collaborators, students that
open science benefits**

everyone

Chandler Sutherland

Kyungyong Seong

Pierre Joubert

Dr Daniil Prigozhin (LBNL)

Grace Stark

Collaborators

Dr Grey Monroe (UC Davis)

Dr Pierre Gladieux (INRAE)

Dr Brian Staskawicz (IGI)

Dr Louise Glass (UC Berkeley)

Alumni

Dr Janina Tamborski

<https://krasilevalab.org/people>

Implement transparency at all stages of research:

- Grant writing - Google docs
- Notebooks - Benchling
- Ideas and results communication - Slack
- Stocks - Tweet your favorite stock organization tool

Implement transparency at all stages of research:

- Post your code openly - Github, Google Colab
- Share all datasets - Zenodo
- Upload all reagents to databases - Addgene, Seed Stock Centers
- Explain your work online - Twitter, Instagram

Do all of these as you do research - ideally shortly after data generation and validation - not upon publication

Preprint! Preprint! Preprint!

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When do we pre-print? The “K-method”

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A great thread! There is a 5th option - we preprint a full finished ms few weeks before submitting to the journal. The goal is to incorporate peer reviews from community before we submit. Typically, we get 3-4 reviews that way send to us via email.

●● **Sophien Kamoun** @KamounLab

I just published: When to preprint?

At what stage in the life of a research paper should you preprint it? It depends on the circumstances of the study, but there are roughly four options.

link.medium.com/38PnVLRfnsb

Do read a “When to preprint” guide by Sophien Kamoun

When to preprint?
Whenever it works for you and co-authors.
There is no rule.

Why we preprint early?*

- Incorporate community feedback
- Update our work (version-controlled papers)
- Celebrate our work
- Complete all projects

*We have been preprinting at least 2 weeks and up to several months before journal submission.

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Preprints boost article citations and mentions

The benefits of showing your hand early.

Gemma Conroy

“When well-conducted studies are available early and shared with the right community, they can make a big impact online very quickly, regardless of the journal’s prestige or citation impact.”

*Nicholas Fraser, a bibliometrics researcher
the Leibniz Information Centre for Economics*

In sum

1. **Convince people** to practice **Open Science**
2. Implement **Transparency**
3. Think of your **Audiences** and **Modern tools**
4. Preprint! **Preprint!** Preprint!

"The Improvement" by Rene Magritte, 1962